

Knowledge based Chords Manipulation in MES

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Abstract : Chord formation in western music notations is an intelligent art form which is learnt over the years by a musician to acquire it. Still it is a question of creativity that brings the perfect chord sequence that matches music score. This work focuses on the process of forming chords using a custom-designed knowledgebase (KB) of Music Expert System. An optimal Chord-Set for a given music score is arrived by using the chord-pool in the KB and the finding the chord match using Jusic Distance (JD). Conceptual Graph based knowledge representation model is followed for knowledge storage and retrieval in the knowledgebase

Keywords : Knowledge, Music, Representation, Knowledgebase, Chord-Set

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